

**METHODOLOGY OF ATTENTION DEVELOPMENT IN MEDICAL CHEMISTRY
LESSONS**

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SUMMARY

Concentration of attention and directing it to the assimilation of necessary information remains one of the most important problems of our time. Because in a huge flow of information it is very difficult to select and study the most important. One of the tools that play an important role in increasing attention is the use of didactic means. The article describes methods that help to increase attention, focus it and distribute it with the help of didactic means. It is also illustrated with concrete examples.

Key words: didactic games and tools, work with text, illustrated applications, table didactic tools, puzzles.

МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ ВНИМАНИЯ НА УРОКАХ МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ХИМИИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Концентрация внимания и направление его на усвоение необходимой информации остается одной из важнейших проблем современности. Потому что в огромном потоке информации очень сложно выделить и изучить самое важное. Одним из инструментов, играющих важную роль в повышении внимания, является использование дидактических средств. В статье описываются методы, помогающие повысить внимание, сосредоточить его и распределить с помощью дидактических средств. Он также проиллюстрирован конкретными примерами.

Ключевые слова: дидактические игры и средства, работа с текстом, иллюстрированные приложения, табличные дидактические средства, головоломки.

Introduction. One of the main goals of medical education is to prepare health professionals with good clinical competence and social communication skills. Because the presence and harmony of these qualities plays a very important role in solving complex health problems. Medical chemistry, a subject studied in medical schools, seems to play the role of a “villain” who intimidates students with its vast information base. Vogel (1993) says that every subject in the university claims to be an essential part of medicine and makes such demands on students that eventually the student wonders, “Do I really need this course?” [1].

Along with such problems, the “disease” of attention deficit, which has become one of the most important problems of the last decade, is becoming increasingly relevant among students. Attention is the most important link of cognitive processes and undoubtedly participates in the organization of cognitive activity of students, providing “orientation in the surrounding reality and selection of the content of conscious human experience” [2].

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Attention is a process and a state of readiness of the subject to perceive essential information and to fulfill the set tasks [3]. A large number of scientific works devoted to the problems of the role of attention in the education of children are carried out by domestic and foreign scientists: T. Ribo, B.G. Ananyev, A.V. Zaporozhyye, A.N. Leontiev, S.P. Rubinstein, W. Wundt. Russian psychologist N.F. Dobrynin emphasizes that attention is a specific type of mental activity that manifests itself in the process of choosing and carrying out this or that activity [4].

The following characteristics of attention are studied:

Concentration of attention is a person's ability to focus on the main thing in his or her activity, distracting himself or herself from anything beyond the task at hand.

The ability to sustain attention, to maintain focused attention for a sufficient amount of time necessary to perform a particular activity, and to resist distractions and random interference during the activity.

The amount of attention is characterized by the number of objects that can be perceived simultaneously with equal clarity and accuracy.

Distributed attention is a property associated with the ability to successfully perform (combine) two or more different activities (several actions) simultaneously.

Attention switching is manifested in the subject's conscious transition from one type of activity to another, from one action to another. This step may be taken as part of a conscious behavioral program or because of the need to engage in a new activity in response to changing circumstances or for recreational purposes.

Therefore, since each characteristic and change in attention is a unique process, we need to study them and be able to guide them properly so that learners can acquire quality knowledge.

Many works have investigated the root causes of these attitudes and recommended the use of didactic games as an optimal solution.

The development of didactic games as a pedagogical method was due to the emergence of interest in play activities, or more precisely, in their influence on children, on the part of practicing teachers who saw the great possibilities of development based on play [5].

Materials and methods: to conduct a survey of teachers and medical students; to study and analyze the misconceptions that arise among students regarding various chemical laws and processes when teaching medical chemistry; to determine the optimal time for conducting didactic games by students during the lesson; to identify ways to form integrative links in the content of tasks.

The use of didactic games in the learning process increases students' interest in the study of science and creates new conditions for understanding chemistry; Didactic materials enrich the content of the subject, which allows to modernize chemical education in medical schools and bring the development of students' professional skills to a qualitative level.

Below is the methodology of teaching on the topic "Nucleic acids" using didactic materials.

This type of teaching is a practical seminar, which mainly reinforces the knowledge gained in theoretical training. In this case, one of the methods that activate students' attention and increase its volume - "Work with text" - is effectively used.

Find the missing words in the text.

Cells contain...different types of nucleic acids. These biopolymers are made up of monomers such as.... Each monomer is made up of ..., ..., These components are connected to each other by ... bonds. A DNA molecule contains the following nitrogenous bases.... An RNA molecule contains the following nitrogenous bases ... In order for the pyrimidine bases to form a complementary pair, they

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must be in ... (lactam) tautomeric state, otherwise a mutation will occur. The Human Genome Project began in ... (1990) and was led by the famous scientist ... (James Watson).

Also, a game of "What has changed?" A question sheet is handed out. It will provide complete information. Students try to memorize the information for two minutes. A blank sheet is then handed out to the students. Students try to fill it in with the information they remember.

Fill in the table with the appropriate information

Types of NA	Cell location	Nukleotides	
		Carbohydrates	Nitrogen bases

In the next task, you will be given the opportunity to choose the correct option from two choices:

Select the correct answer.

1. Monomers of nucleic acids (amino acids, nucleotides)
2. What are the components of a nucleoside? (amino acid, nitrogenous base, phosphoric acid, carbohydrate)
3. Who discovered the rule of additionality? (Watson, Chargaff)
4. What is the structure of DNA? (1 chain, double helix).
5. In what tautomeric state do pyrimidine bases exist in the nucleic acid chain? (actam, lactam).
6. What nitrogenous base distinguishes DNA from RNA? (thymine, uracil)

Another interesting and suitable didactic game for group work is "Cat in the Bag". In this case, each group chooses a question of a certain difficulty from a set of corresponding questions. If the answer is correct, he/she gets the corresponding point.

"Cat in the Bag".

Biopolimers

Peptides	10	20	30
Carbohydrates	10	20	30
Nucleic acids	10	20	30
Biopolimers in medicine	10	20	30

Protein:

10. How many different amino acids are mainly found in living organisms? (Mostly 20 types.)
20. Give a systematic name to glycine. (2-aminoethanoic acid)
30. Give an example of an aromatic amino acid? (Phenylalanine, tyrosine)

Carbohydrates:

10. Why can't the human body digest cellobiose? (Because the human body lacks the enzyme that breaks down cellobiose, β -glucosidase)

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20. What monosaccharides does the lactose molecule consist of? (D-galactopyranose and D-glucopyranose).

30. What is the hydroxyl group of a polyacetal called? (glycoside)

Nucleic Acids

10. Who discovered the double helix of DNA and when? (Discovered by J. Watson and F. Crick in 1953)

20. What parts of the nucleic acid chain do phosphodiester bonds connect? (Binds carbohydrate residues in the molecule)

30. What tautomer of thymine can form a complementary pair with adenine? (Lactam form)

Biopolymers in Medicine

10. What is the name of the biopolymer first discovered in the cell nucleus? (Nucleic acid)

20. Name the first polypeptide synthesized in the laboratory. It is used to stop bleeding and stimulate uterine contractions. (Oxytocin)

30. Due to what properties is hyaluronic acid used in cosmetology? (retains moisture in the skin, prevents bacterial penetration)

Results. We concluded that the above didactic means are able to attract students' attention and focus them on mastering the main content of the lesson. This experiment also showed its results in pilot tests [6].

1. In order for students to fully internalize knowledge during the lesson and be able to apply it in practice, the teacher needs to abandon the method of "information delivery";

2. The first step in the proper organization of the lesson is to attract the students' attention and explain to them that the knowledge they are learning today is very important. To do this, you need to find interesting information within the topic and deliver it to the student in a unique way. For example, "Would you like to have your own clone?" (On the topic of nucleic acids) or "Why do you think people living in Alaska have the lowest rate of cardiovascular disease?" (On the topic of lipids).

3- Text questions play a very important role in PISA tasks used to test students' knowledge. Because it is by the text question that one can determine how much attention is developed. Applying this experience to university students is also useful.

These results prompted us to revise the tasks used in teaching medical chemistry and to enrich them with content that promotes attention development.

Conclusion: We proposed the following solutions for teachers who want to help students not only to improve their competence through the use of relevant skills and qualifications, but also to develop their creativity and critical thinking within chemistry and other clinical disciplines.

1. organize didactic games by topics and shape them in such a way as to correct some misconceptions (stereotypes) formed in the students' minds;

2. Distribute tasks of this kind from simple to complex and give them in number from one to five during the lesson;

3. Set a time limit for performing the tasks - no more than 10-12 minutes;

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